

Intrinsically disordered regions-based aquareceptors

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In the emerging field of gasocrinology, it is important not only to identify all the gasoreceptors involved in gasocrine signaling, as well as those that exhibit duality or multimodality in sensing other molecules or factors.^{1,2} Earlier, I proposed that hemoglobin acts an oxygen gasoreceptor in a proto- or split-component signal transduction system (STS).³⁻⁵ Additionally, I proposed that hemoglobin is also one of the heme-based water-sensing aquareceptors.⁶ This rationale can be extended to other hemoproteins as well. For example, the *Arabidopsis thaliana* Delay of Germination-1 (DOG1) protein can be considered a potential gasoreceptor or aquareceptor.⁷ However, the sensing domain in receptors can vary.⁸ This raises the question: apart from heme domain-containing globin-based aquareceptors, are there other domain-based aquareceptors? Since some intrinsically disordered region (IDR) domain-containing proteins have water-sensing potential, I propose that IDR-domain containing proteins are potential water-sensing aquareceptors in split-, proto-, two-, one-, or multi-component STS. Therefore, the *A. thaliana* sterile alpha motif (SAM)-containing protein, SAM8 and FLOE1 and human Rel family transcription factor NFAT5 are also potential aquareceptor in split-component STS.⁹⁻
¹¹ However, further experiments are needed to determine if it is only an aquareceptor, a receptor for other ions, or an aquareceptor that exhibits duality or multimodality.¹² Finally, it is worth also considering the role of potential IDR-like nucleic acids as potential water-sensing aquareceptors.¹³⁻¹⁵

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